

Characteristics of the elements considered in the hydraulic modelling

Links (conduits, pumps valves) are identified by the index i . N_C conduits are installed in the WDN. The hydraulic resistance depends on the length L_i , the diameter D_i , and on the equivalent roughness ε_i (according to the Colebrook-White's approach). In pipes the flow velocity is V_i and the flow rate is Q_i . Along the i -th pipe, distributed leakages occur. Leakages depend on the diameter, age of material of the pipe, and on the pressure. The leakage per unit length is $q_{L,i} = C_{L,i} \cdot [P_i(x_i)]^{0.5}$, where $P_i(x_i)$ is the pressure at the location x_i in the i -th pipe, whereas $C_{L,i}$ is a leakage coefficient that takes into account the diameter, age, material and condition of the conduit.

Pumps are characterized by the pump-curves $C_{P,i}(\Delta H_{P,i}, Q_{P,i})$, where $\Delta H_{P,i}$ is the total head and $Q_{P,i}$ is the flow rate. N_P pumps are installed in the WDN. The (constant) efficiency of pumps is η_i , whereas the cost of energy is c_E . Pumps are dynamic elements that can be switched on/off by controls, so the additional variable $s_{P,i}$ is defined to monitor the status of the machine. For what concerns valves, here we only consider throttle control valves with headloss coefficient $C_{V,i}$ that satisfies the equation $\Delta H_{V,i} = C_{V,i} [2Q_{V,i} / (g\pi D_{V,i}^2)]^2$ where $Q_{V,i}$ is the flow through valve, $\Delta H_{V,i}$ is the head drop across the valve, $D_{V,i}$ is the nominal diameter of the valve. N_V valves are installed in the WDN. Similar to pumps, valves are dynamic elements that can be switched on/off by controls, so the additional variable $s_{V,i}$ (that monitor the status of the valve) is defined.

Junctions are identified by the index j . N_J junctions are installed in the WDN. Junctions are characterized by the users' demand $Q_{D,j}$, by the leakage $Q_{L,j}$ and by the elevation z_j . Users require the time-varying demand $Q_{DU,j}(t)$, but the actual outflow that can be provided by the WDN is constrained by pressure. In particular, the parameter $P_{\min,j}$ is the minimum pressure at the j -junction so that the outflow provided by the network can be equal or larger than the demand required by users. On the other hand, P_j is the (possibly time-varying) pressure at the j -junction. When $P_j \geq P_{\min,j}$, the outflow from the j -junction is $Q_{D,j} = Q_{DU,j}(t)$ (i.e., the users' demand is fully satisfied). When $P_j < P_{\min,j}$, the outflow is $Q_{D,j} < Q_{DU,j}(t)$. The users' demand cannot be fully satisfied, and the demand deficit is $\Delta Q_j(t) = Q_{DU,j} - Q_{D,j}(t)$. It should be finally remarked that the time-varying demand can be written as $Q_{DU,j}(t) = \bar{Q}_{DU,j} \Pi_j(t)$, where $\bar{Q}_{DU,j}$ is the (usually daily-) average demand, whereas $\Pi_j(t)$ is a time pattern that describes the temporal variations. In this study, time variations are limited to a weekly typical pattern with hourly time-steps.

Additional elements of a WDN are tanks, identified by the index τ . N_T tanks are installed in the WDN. Tanks are characterized by the level $H_{T,\tau}(t)$, maximum level $H_{\max,\tau}$, minimum level $H_{\min,\tau}$, elevation of bottom $z_{T,\tau}$ and by the radius $R_{T,\tau}$. Similar to pumps and valves, tanks are dynamic elements, and to fully describe a hydraulic problem it is necessary to know the tanks' initial level $H_{0,\tau}$. The last considered physical elements of WDN are reservoirs, identified by the index r . N_{Res} reservoirs are installed in the WDN, and are characterized by the head $H_{Res,r}$.

Additional (intangible) elements that deeply affect the dynamics of a WDN are controls. Controls are a set of logical rules that modify the status of valves and pumps according to a set of state variables. State variables can be: (i) the pressure in prescribed nodes; (ii) the level of tanks; (iii) the time of the day; (iv) the flow rate in some prescribed link.

For the purpose of this study, it necessary to consider the compliance of the service provided by the Water Utility with the contracts signed between the Water Utility and customers. The key parameter in this case is the minimum pressure that the Water Utility should guarantee to customers, namely P_{cmp} .

Implementation of modelling and algorithms

Figure 2 reports the diagram of the algorithm adopted to model the sequence of replacement of all links listed in **R**. The core of the algorithm is to simulate a WDN with evolving topology and hydraulic characteristics. To do that, a cycle of simulations of the WDN are done over the time t (yellow rectangles in figure 2). The flow of time is sometimes interrupted to perform the required modifications of topology or hydraulic characteristics. These interruptions are done with the help of two parameters: t_{\max} and “type”. The parameter t_{\max} set the time when simulations on the WDN are to be stopped, and its characteristics are to be updated (orange rhombus in figure 2). The parameter “type” set the type of modification to be performed: closure of the pipe or opening of the pipe with updated diameter, roughness, leakages (green rhombus in figure 2). To better understand the algorithm, a typical cycle (see arrows in figure 2) is followed and discussed.

The first step is to load all data of the WDN prior to renovation works. With this data, an input file for a WDN modelling software can be produced. In this work, EPANet was used, and so an “.inp” file was written. An additional task of this first step is to load the calendar time of each operation for each pipe to be replaced. We recall that: (i) $t_{1,k}$ is the calendar time when the k –th pipe is disconnected from the network; (ii) $t_{2,k}$ is the calendar time the k –th pipe is connected back to the network, with updated values of roughness and diameter; (iii) the renovation works begin at $t = t_0$ and end at $t = t_0 + T_W$.

The second step is to initialize the time at the value $t = t_0$, and set $t_{\max} = t_{1,k}$ and type=close. The first setting defines the next calendar time in which a modification of the network is to be performed. The second setting defines the type of the next modification to be performed.

The third step is to simulate the network behavior until $t \leq t_{\max}$ (yellow rectangles in figure 2). For each time step Δt the values of pressure and demand at junctions are saved in the time series $P_j(t)$ and $Q_j(t)$. Other data that are saved are the level of tanks $H_{T,\tau}(t)$; the status (open/close; on/off) of other dynamical elements (e.g., valves/pumps).

When t exceeds t_{\max} , the cyclic modelling of the WDN is interrupted (orange rhombus in figure 2). The check $t < t_{end}$ with $t_{end} = t_0 + T_W$ is performed (gray rhombus in figure 2). If negative (i.e., renovation works haven’t yet been completed) an operation on pipes is performed. To do that, the saved levels of tanks $H_{T,\tau}(t)$ and the status of all dynamical elements is loaded. Then, two paths can be followed, depending on the operations to be performed (green rhombus in figure 2).

One possible operation is the closure of the pipe (pink rectangles). This entails to: (i) set to zero the leakages induced by the k –th pipe at the junctions where the US and DS merge (i.e., the terms $Q_{L,k,j}$); and (ii) disconnect the pipe (in EPANet: set the pipe’s status to “close”). In addition, it is set the new value $t_{\max} = t_{2,k}$ (the calendar time when the new pipe will be put in service) and type=replace (i.e., the next operation will be to put in service the new pipe).

The other possible operation is to put in service the new pipe (light blue rectangles). This entails to: (i) modify the roughness and diameter of the k –th pipe to the new values; (ii) connect the pipe (in EPANet: set the pipe’s status to “open”); and (iii) keep the leakages induced by the k –th pipe at the junctions where the US and DS merge to zero (i.e., the terms $Q_{L,k,j}$). In addition, it is set the new value $t_{\max} = t_{1,k+1}$ (the calendar time when the next pipe to be replaced ($k + 1$) will be closed and disconnected); and type=close (i.e., the next operation will be to close the ($k + 1$) –th pipe).

In order to implement these modifications, a new input file for a WDN modelling software (an EPANet “.inp” file in this specific case) is written. After this point, new simulations with the updated network can be performed (see the red arrow in figure 2). It should be noted that we choose the MATLAB toolkit for EPANet (see [14]) to perform this long sequence of operations.

To sum up, the typical results of one simulation of WDN renovations (see the rectangle below the gray rhombus in figure 2) are: (i) the time series of pressure in each junctions $P_j(t)$; the time series of the demand in each junction $Q_j(t)$.

These time series can be analyzed, and can be used to evaluate additional time-series useful for determining the effect of the replacement works on users, such as: (i) the demand deficit, evaluated as the difference between the flow rate wanted by users and the flowrate provided by the network, i.e., $\Delta Q_j(t) = Q_{DU,j} - Q_{D,j}(t)$; (ii) the time series of leakages in all junction $Q_{L,j}$; (iii) the time series of pressure $P_j(t)$. It should be noted that the time series span in the time interval $[t_0, t_0 + T_W]$ with the timestep Δt .

Figure 3. Algorithm adopted to model a sequence of operations for the renovation of water distribution networks. Colors are used to guide the reader in the algorithm description provided in the main text.

Algorithm for the optimization of the sequence of replacement

In order to optimize the sequence of replacement, the so called “Population Based Incremental Learning (PBIL) algorithm” is used. In order to understand how to implement this algorithm, the definition of a number of variables and parameters is first required. Vector \mathbf{I} lists all links in the network. Vector \mathbf{R} includes all links to be replaced. $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbf{I}$ and the number of elements of \mathbf{R} is N_R . The number of phases of link replacement is N_m . In principle, N_m can be different from N_R , as more links can be replaced during one single phase. Here we focus on the case $N_m = N_R$.

With the definitions previously provided, it becomes clear that the optimization algorithm is aimed at determining the best sequence of the elements listed in the vector \mathbf{R} . In this regard, “best sequence” means that the cost associated with the sequence of \mathbf{R} is minimum.

The steps implemented to apply the PBIL algorithm to the specific are as follows.

- Step 1 – Definition of the probability matrix. Firstly, the probability matrix \mathbf{P}^s with size $N_R \times N_R$ is defined. Each element of the matrix $\mathbf{P}^s(k, m)$ is the probability that the pipe k will be replaced during the phase m . The superscript s refers to the current iteration in the optimization algorithm. At the beginning of the optimization ($s = 1$) all the elements of \mathbf{P}^s are equal to $1/N_R$ (same probability).
- Step 2 – Generation of a random sequence of pipe replacement (called sequence vector). For each pipe k^* , the phase m during which the pipe will be replaced is determined. This is done generating sample values (i.e., random extraction) from the probability distributions $\mathbf{P}^s(k^*, m)$. One example of sequence vector is $J = [i_5, i_3, i_2, i_1, i_4, \dots, i_{N_R}]$, where i_m is the index (i) of the pipe to be replaced during phase m .
- Step 3 – Generation of the population. In this step, a population of N_{rdm} sequence vectors J_η with $\eta = 1: N_{rdm}$ is created. The sequence vectors are obtained according to Step 2. The population vector is thus $\mathbf{J} = [J_1, J_2, \dots, J_{N_{rdm}}]$.
- Step 4 – Reparation of the sequence vectors. The elements i_m of the η –th sequence vector are randomly chosen from the vector \mathbf{R} . These elements are supposed to be unique in each sequence vectors J_η of the population \mathbf{J} , as each pipe will be changed once in each sequence of operation. The algorithm checks if there are repetitive elements, and replace them with new randomly chosen elements. The procedure is repeated until each sequence vectors J_η of the population \mathbf{J} includes all the elements of the matrix \mathbf{R} .
- Step 5 – Cost evaluation for each sequence vector. The cost incurred during the replacement works is calculated for each sequence vector that make up the population. The sequence vector that provides the lowest cost among the entire population is J^* .
- Step 6 -Update of the probability matrix. Each row (index k) of the probability matrix in the algorithm at the iteration $s + 1$ will be updated as follows. At first, the condition $J^*(k) = i_m$ is checked for each element of $J^*(k)$, i.e., $k = 1: N_R$. The condition identifies when –in the most convenient sequence found so far– the k –th pipe is replaced during the m –th phase. When the condition holds true, the probability of such an event is increased. This is done modifying the probability matrix as $\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) = (1 - LR) \times P^s(k, m) + LR$, where LR is the learning rate. When the condition doesn't hold true, the probability of such an event occurring is reduced. Again, this is done modifying the probability matrix as $\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) = (1 - LR) \times P^s(k, m)$.
- Step 7 -Probability matrix mutation. During optimization, it is possible for algorithms to get stuck in local optimal solution. Mutations are thus used to escape from these local minimums. In each row k of the probability matrix \mathbf{P}^{s+1} , one element is randomly selected. The selection is done with mutation probability f . The so called “direction of mutation” is then randomly determined as $d_f = (-1 \text{ or } 1)$. Mutations are then applied on the row k as follows. For the location (k, m) , $\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) = \left[\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) \times (1 - (d_f \times \Delta f)) \right] + (d_f \times \Delta f)$; for locations

other than (k, m) in row k : $\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) = \left[\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) \times \left(1 - (d_f \times \Delta f) \right) \right]$, where Δf is the value of the mutation shift. If $\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) > 1$ the condition $\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) = 1$ is set, whereas if $\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) < 0$ the condition $\mathbf{P}^{s+1}(k, m) = 0$ is set.

- Step 8 - Check the algorithm stop criteria. If the number of prescribed iterations of the algorithms s has reached the pre-set number of iterations NI to be performed, the algorithm is stopped, otherwise another iteration begins from Step 2.